

Synthesis, Characterization and Screening of Antibacterial Activity of Some New Mannich Bases

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THE use of Mannich bases as analgesic¹, antibacterial² and anti-inflammatory³ compounds encouraged us to synthesize some new Mannich bases. A survey of literature reveals that Ram and Pandey⁴ have synthesized a number of Mannich bases from 5-substituted-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione and its derivatives and from 3-methyl-isooxazolin-5-one. Singh, Bindal and Dixit⁵ prepared these bases from isovaleramide. Werner and Walter⁶ prepared Mannich bases by treating 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone with formaldehyde and dimethylamine. But Mannich bases have not yet been synthesized from resacetophenone, 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone, gallacetophenone, phloroacetophenone, 2-acetylbenzofuran, *p*-phenylacetophenone and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin. So the authors thought to synthesize Mannich bases from these substituted ketones and to test the antibacterial activity of some of these bases.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using Beckmann spectrophotometer. All the m.p. are uncorrected and taken in open capillary.

General Procedure for the Synthesis of Mannich Bases :

To a cold ethanolic (95 %) solution of ketone (0.02 mole), formaldehyde (2 ml, 40%) was added and left in ice-mix. for a few minutes. To the cold mix. an amine (0.02 mole) solution in ethanol was added dropwise and with constant stirring and left in ice-mixture with occasional stirring. The time of formation of each base was recorded carefully. The Mannich bases were filtered, washed with distilled water and a little ethanol and recrystallized from a suitable solvent (Table 1).

Resacetophenone⁷, 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone⁸, gallacetophenone⁹, phloroacetophenone¹⁰, *p*-phenylacetophenone¹¹ and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin¹² used in the synthesis of Mannich bases were prepared from literature methods.

In the infra-red spectrum a broad absorption band was observed in the region 3400-3550 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of an intramolecular hydrogen bonded hydroxyl group in the bases. A sharp absorption band in the region 1660-1700 cm⁻¹ indicates $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$. The weak absorption band observed

TABLE I—MANNICH BASES OF ARYL KETONES

Sl. No.	Name of the compounds	Time of formation (hr)	Recrystallizing solvents	m.p. (°C)	Structure formula	Diameter of zone (mm)	Average
1.	β -Phenylamino-2 : 4 D.P.	1	acetone	135	$\begin{array}{c} \text{RCOCH}_2\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{Ph-NH} \end{array}$	13.4, 14.1, 14.3, 14.8, 13.6, 14.0, 14.2, 13.8.	14.02 mm
2.	β -Benzidiny-2 : 4 D.P.	2½ - 3	aq. ethanol	149	$\begin{array}{c} \text{RCOCH}_2\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{A-NH} \end{array}$	12.3, 12.0, 11.8, 12.8, 12.2, 12.3, 13.0, 12.0.	12.30 mm
3.	β -Diphenylamino-2 : 4 D.P.	24	ether solvent	90	$\begin{array}{c} \text{RCOCH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{Ph} \rangle \text{N} \\ \\ \text{Ph} \end{array}$		
4.	β -Phenylamino-2 : 5 D.P.	1	ethanol	235	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1\text{COCH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{Ph-NH} \end{array}$	15.5, 15.0, 15.0, 14.3, 14.0, 14.2, 14.0.	14.55 mm
5.	β -Benzidiny-2 : 5 D.P.	½	aq. ethanol	140	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1\text{COCH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{A-NH} \end{array}$	16.4, 17.2, 16.4, 16.0, 16.2, 16.0, 16.5, 16.6.	16.41 mm
6.	β -Benzidiny-2,3,4 T.P.	½	acetone	180	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_2\text{COCH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{A-NH} \end{array}$		
7.	β -(α)-Naphthyl-amino-2,3,4 T.P.	3½	aq. ethanol	167	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_2\text{COCH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{B} \\ \\ \text{A-NH} \end{array}$	22.0, 21.6, 22.0, 22.2, 21.8, 22.0, 21.8, 22.0.	21.92 mm
8.	β -Benzidiny-2,4,6-T.P.	½	ethanol	above 320	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}_2\text{COCH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{A-NH} \end{array}$		

* For correspondence.

(Table 1 Contd.)

9.	β -(α)-Naphthyl-amino-2,4,6 T.P.	2	ethanol	above 320	$R_2COCH_2-CH_2$ NH B		
10.	2-(β)-Phenylamino-propionyl benzofuran	1	acetone	184	$R_4COCH_2-CH_2$ Ph-NH		
11.	β -Benzidiny-(<i>p</i>)-phenyl P.	$\frac{1}{2}$	aq. ethanol	147	$R_2COCH_2CH_2$ A-NH		
12.	β -(α)-Naphthyl-amino-(<i>p</i>)-phenyl P.	$1\frac{1}{2}$	acetone	185	$R_2COCH_2CH_2$ B-NH Ph-NH	21.0, 21.0, 21.8, 21.8, 20.8, 20.7.	21.18 mm
13.	3-(β)-Phenylamino propionyl-4-hydroxy-coumarin	1	ethanol	165	$R_2COCH_2CH_2$ B-NH Ph-NH		

D=Dihydroxy, T=Trihydroxy, P=Propiophenone, Ph=Phenyl,

in the region 3300-3350 cm^{-1} is characteristic of $\nu(-NH)$.

The N.M.R. spectrum of the Mannich bases in $CdCl_2$ shows a multiplet from 6.88 δ to 7.48 δ and a sharp singlet at 4.69 δ indicating the presence of the aromatic and methylene protons, respectively. The absorption of amino proton is observed at 3.30 δ .

Screening for Antibacterial Activity :

The compounds 1, 2, 4, 5, 7 and 12 listed in Table 1 were screened for their inhibitory effects against two organisms viz., *Bacillus cereus* (Gram positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative) by agar diffusion technique^{1,8} and the results obtained are depicted in Table 1. The concentration of the soln. was 0.5 mg/ml in D.M.F. The bases were found to exhibit activity against *Bacillus cereus* only. Bacterial cultures were maintained at Microbiology Department of Central Pharmaceutical Laboratory, New Rajnagar, Ghaziabad.

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New 5-Arylamino-2[N-(2'-Mercaptoacetylamino-4'-Arylthiazolo)]-Thiadiazoles(III) : as AChE Inhibitors

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THIADIAZOLES are known as potent fungicide¹, insecticide² and bactericide³. 5-Acylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-sulfonamide, an efficient pre- and postemergent herbicide has been reported by Kirkpatrick⁴.